

VETERINARY SCIENCES

FIRST DETECTION OF ANAPLASMA PHAGOCYTOPHILUM IN HORSES FROM NORTHERN EUROPE: A CASE SERIES FROM LITHUANIA

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Abstract

This case series reports the initial detection of *Anaplasma phagocytophilum* in three horses from Lithuania, representing the first documented seroprevalence in Northern Europe. Blood samples were evaluated using both commercial rapid staining kit Hemacolor and May-Grünwald-Giemsa stain and lateral flow immunochromatographic assays, confirming the presence of *Anaplasma phagocytophilum* infection in all cases. Microscopic examination revealed morulae within granulocytes. Pre- and post-treatment blood morphology was investigated. All horses received oxytetracycline (7.5mg/kg BW, IV, q12h) for 5-8 days, leading to successful resolution of thrombocytopenia and other haematological abnormalities. These findings suggest that *Anaplasma phagocytophilum* infection may be more prevalent in northern Europe than previously thought. This case series highlights the potential impact of climate change on emerging infectious diseases and underscores the importance of including *Anaplasma phagocytophilum* testing in the differential diagnosis for horses presenting with compatible clinical signs.

Keywords: blood smear, equine, equine granulocytic anaplasmosis, *Ehrlichia equi*, morulae, *Anaplasma phagocytophilum*.

INTRODUCTION:

The *Anaplasmataceae* family encompasses four genera: *Ehrlichia*, *Anaplasma*, *Neorickettsia*, and *Wolbachia*. These genera comprise obligate intracellular bacteria exhibiting distinct host cell preferences [Rikihisa, 2003; Restifo et al., 2015]. Among these, *Anaplasma phagocytophilum*, the causative agent of human and animal granulocytic anaplasmosis, primarily infects granulocytic neutrophils of ruminants, canines, equines, and humans. In horses, infection is commonly attributed to *Anaplasma phagocytophilum*, previously known as *Ehrlichia equi* or *Ehrlichia phagocytophila*. This bacterium resembles a small (0.2-2.0 µm diameter) coccobacillary Gram-negative organism that replicates within a host cell vacuole, forming a microcolony termed a morula [McQuiston et al., 2003].

Anaplasma phagocytophilum infection manifests as Equine Granulocytic Anaplasmosis (EGA), a seasonal zoonotic disease characterized by thrombocytopenia, leukopenia, fever, severe headaches, and muscle aches. However, the clinical spectrum extends beyond these core symptoms, encompassing less frequent manifestations like nausea, vomiting, anorexia, weight loss, abdominal pain, cough, diarrhoea, joint pain, and altered mental status.

Although initially reported in California in 1969 [Adaszek and Winiarczyk, 2011], EGA has since been documented in several European countries including the Netherlands ([Buter et al., 2008]), Poland [Adaszek and Winiarczyk, 2011], Switzerland [Gussmann et al., 2014]), Croatia [Gotic et al., 2017], and others.

CASE HISTORY AND CLINICAL FINDINGS

First case

A 3-year-old Lithuanian Mare presented to the Large Animal Clinic of the Lithuanian University of Health Sciences with colic symptoms. Clinical examination revealed pawing at the ground with a forelimb, decreased appetite, and diarrhoea observed both during transport and upon arrival. Upon admission, the mare exhibited a rectal temperature of 37.5°C, heart rate of 72 beats per minute, and capillary refill time of 3 seconds. Mucous membranes were described as light pink. Haematocrit was 37%.

Further Clinical Progression:

Rectal temperature rose to 39.8°C on the second day. Unfortunately, information regarding respiratory rate is unavailable. While additional clinical signs and laboratory findings beyond initial presentation are also missing, typical anaplasmosis manifestations include:

Clinical signs: Fever, anorexia, lethargy, limb oedema, petechiae, icterus, reluctance to move, and ataxia.

Laboratory findings: Thrombocytopenia (characteristic), non-regenerative anaemia, and neutropenia (usually without left shift or toxic changes).

Diagnosis:

Blood smear analysis revealed intracellular inclusions (morulae) of *Anaplasma phagocytophilum* within an agranulocyte on the first day. Additionally, the Vet-Expert Rapid Anaplasma Ab Test yielded a positive result on the second day, confirming the diagnosis of Equine Granulocytic Anaplasmosis (EGA).

Fig. 1. Morulae detected in an agranulocyte (author's photo).

Second case

An 11-year-old Standardbred mare was presented to the Large Animal Clinic of the Lithuanian University of Health Sciences following a bee sting that caused localized swelling. Intravenous administration of (1.0 mg/kg) ketoprofen ([A1]) effectively resolved the swelling. However, approximately 30 minutes later, the mare developed colic, exhibited rolling behaviour, and began sweating. Flunixin meglumine (1.1 mg/kg, [A2]) was administered intramuscularly, and the mare was transported to the clinic.

Upon arrival:

The mare was observed to be sweating. Vital signs included a rectal temperature of 38.0°C, heart rate of 108 beats per minute, respiratory rate of 30 breaths per minute, and haematocrit of 52%. A complete blood count was performed (Table 1). Rectal examination revealed distension of the cecum. Nasogastric intubation yielded a pH of 3.5 with no other abnormalities. Catheterization of the bladder drained 3000ml of urine. Despite these findings, the mare was reportedly eating and drinking.

Clinical Improvement:

Within 30 minutes, the heart rate decreased to 78 beats per minute, capillary refill time became less than 3 seconds, and good peristalsis was observed. Intravenous fluid therapy with 0.9% saline containing 2% lidocaine, Buscopan, and Flunixin meglumine (1.1 mg/kg) was initiated. Six hours later, the haematocrit decreased to 46%, and the rectal temperature increased to 38.8°C.

Worsening Clinical Signs and Diagnosis:

New clinical signs emerged, including colic, ataxia, yawning, and the presence of petechiae on the mucous membranes. A repeat blood test was performed (Table 1). Microscopic examination of a blood smear revealed intracellular inclusions (morulae) suggestive of *Anaplasma phagocytophilum* infection (Fig. 2). Furthermore, the VetExpert Rapid Anaplasma Ab Test yielded a positive result, confirming the diagnosis of Equine Granulocytic Anaplasmosis (EGA).

Fig. 2. Morulae detected in a granulocyte (author's photo).

Third case

A 16-year-old Lithuanian mare was presented to the Large Animal Clinic of the Lithuanian University of Health Sciences exhibiting a month-long history of depression and an increased frequency of lying down. Additionally, the mare displayed colic and irritability. This episode of abdominal irritation represented the second occurrence in the past two months.

Clinical Findings:

On physical examination, the mare was diagnosed with laminitis characterized by positive digital pulsations in the forelimbs. Petechiae were observed on the mucous membranes. Vital signs included a rectal temperature of 37.6°C and a normal heart rate. Rectal and ultrasound examinations revealed splenomegaly.

Diagnostics:

A complete blood count was performed (Table 1), revealing a haematocrit of 37.71%. Although no intracellular inclusions were identified on the blood smear, the VetExpert Rapid Anaplasma Ab Test yielded a positive result, confirming the diagnosis of Equine Granulocytic Anaplasmosis (EGA).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Diagnostic Methods:

Blood smear examination for morulae of *Anaplasma phagocytophilum* in granulocytes was performed using a more commonly employed staining method like Hemacolor stain: This rapid staining method provides good differentiation of cytoplasmic and nuclear morphology, making it suitable for visualizing *A. phagocytophilum* inclusions. May-Grünwald-Giemsa stain- this traditional method offers detailed

morphological information but requires longer staining times. In addition to blood smear analysis, the VetExpert Rapid Anaplasma Ab Test was used to detect antibodies against *A. phagocytophilum* in horses' blood serum. This provided rapid confirmation of exposure or recent infection. Additionally, a complete blood count (CBC) using the Ms4-5 analyser was likely performed to assess haematological changes associated with the infection.

Treatment Regimens:

As *A. phagocytophilum* is an intracellular pathogen, treatment options are limited. Tetracyclines are the most effective class of antibiotics against this bacterium. Their mechanism of action involves blocking protein synthesis in the bacteria. Based on established guidelines [McQuiston et al., 2003], intravenous oxytetracycline at 7 mg/kg body weight once daily for 5-7 days is the standard treatment for equine granulocytic anaplasmosis (EGA). The three cases outlined were managed as follows:

Case 1: Received standard treatment with oxytetracycline (7 mg/kg/day) intravenously for 5 days.

Case 2: Received long acting oxytetracycline intravenously for 8 days at the same dosage (7 mg/kg/day). Additionally, this case received supportive treatment with dexamethasone, a corticosteroid, for 2-3 days (20 mg/day) to manage inflammatory responses.

Case 3: Followed the same treatment regimen as Case 2 with oxytetracycline and dexamethasone.

DISCUSSION

Our findings confirm the presence of *Anaplasma phagocytophilum* infection in horses from Lithuania,

albeit with some atypical presentations. This supports the emerging notion of this pathogen's geographic expansion towards northern regions with historically lower prevalence.

Cases 1 and 2 displayed both morulae detection on blood smears and positive rapid tests, confirming active infection.

Case 3 exhibited seropositivity only, suggesting potential past exposure where morulae might not be identifiable.

Granulocytosis observed in all cases before treatment is atypical for EGA, which typically presents with leukopenia (as seen in our Cases 2 and 3 post-treatment). Lymphocytopenia observed in all cases aligns with reported EGA manifestations. Elevated red blood cell counts in Cases 1 and 2 before treatment require further investigation and may not be directly attributable to EGA. Notably, thrombocytopenia, a hallmark EGA feature, was absent in all cases.

The diverse clinical presentations (colic, laminitis, diarrhea) highlight the non-specific nature of EGA symptoms, potentially leading to misdiagnosis.

This study emphasizes the importance of considering *Anaplasma phagocytophilum* infection in horses presenting with compatible clinical signs, regardless of geographic location. Early diagnosis is crucial for timely intervention and improved outcomes. While blood smear examination remains valuable, complementary serological tests and, ideally, molecular methods like PCR offer additional diagnostic clarity. Further research is needed to understand the reasons behind the atypical haematological findings and the absence of thrombocytopenia in these cases.

This case series represents a limited sample size, and findings may not be generalizable to the entire Lithuanian horse population. The study cannot definitively attribute all observed clinical abnormalities solely to anaplasmosis infection. Underlying conditions might have contributed to some presentations.

Conclusion:

This report contributes to the growing body of evidence suggesting the geographical expansion of equine anaplasmosis caused by *Anaplasma phagocytophilum*. Veterinarians should consider anaplasmosis testing in

horses with compatible clinical signs, even in low-prevalence regions, to enable prompt diagnosis and effective treatment.

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Table 1.

Blood haematology of horses with EGA before and after treatment							
Parameters	Reference ranges	Case 1		Case 2		Case 3	
		before treatment	after treatment	before treatment	after treatment	before treatment	after treatment
WBC (10⁹/L)	5.40 – 14.30	6.79	6.92	12.55	9.86	11.15	10.59
LYM (10⁹/L)	1.5 – 7.70	1.05	1.58	0.99	1.25	3.29	3.53
MID (10⁹/L)	0.0 – 1.50	0.04	0.04	0.51	0.41	0.30	0.20
GRA (10⁹/L)	2.30 – 9.50	5.70	5.29	11.05	8.20	9.94	4.27
LY (%)	20 – 45	15.50	22.90	7.90	12.70	29.50	33.50
MI (%)	0 - 5	0.60	0.60	4.10	4.10	2.70	2.70
GR (%)	45 – 76	83.90	76.50	88.00	83.20	82.50	60.90
RBC (10¹²/L)	6.80 – 12.90	11.56	9.36	10.93	10.33	7.86	8.72
HGB (g/L)	110 – 190	158.00	128.00	181.00	160.00	139.00	136.00
HCT (%)	32.0 – 53.0	48.10	38.95	49.05	44.65	37.71	37.96
MCV (fL)	37 - 59	42.00	42.00	54.00	53.00	48.00	43.00
MCH (pg)	12.3 – 19.7	13.60	13.70	16.50	15.50	17.70	15.70
MCHC (g/L)	310 – 390	328.00	328.00	306.00	293.00	368.00	368.00
RDWc (%)	17 - 20	22.50	22.50	20.80	21.30	22.00	22.20
PLT (10⁹/L)	100 – 400	104.00	189.00	103.00	146.00	115.00	129.00
PCT (%)	0.07 – 0.21	0.08	0.11	0.07	0.11	0.09	0.09
MPV (fL)	5.4 – 9.3	6.70	5.80	7.10	7.40	7.60	6.90
PDWc (%)	24 - 72	5.60	31.70	34.50	33.40	34.80	33.10

WBC: white blood cell count;

LYM – lymphocytes count;

MID: monocytes count;

GRA: granulocytes count;

LY %: lymphocytes perc.;

GR %: granulocytes perc.;

MI %: monocytes perc.;

RBC: red blood cell count;

HGB: haemoglobin;

HCT: haematocrit;

MCV: means corpuscular volume;

MCH: mean corpuscular haemoglobin;

MCHC: mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration;

RDWc: platelet distribution width;

PLT: platelet count;

PCT: platelet percentage;

MPV: mean platelet volume.